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Stakeholder perspectives on sustainable vineyard practices in Germany's Mosel region: A multicriteria assessment

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Summary

This research employs a survey of relevant stakeholders to identify low-input farming practices with the potential to mitigate key agronomic and environmental challenges in the Mosel vineyard region (Germany) and enhance their sustainability. Stakeholders are concerned about the future of the Mosel winemaking region as threatened by the lack of farm generational succession and of economic sustainability, as well as suffering problems of excessive fertiliser use and biodiversity loss. Their priorities actions such as: conserving traditional landscapes, recovering traditional crops, reducing soil erosion, and increasing crop profitability. The stakeholders point at minimum tillage, soil mulching, maintenance of natural vegetation on plot edges, green manure, and pheromone control as the most adequate farming practices for the area. Using TOPSIS (Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution) multi-criteria analysis, these practices have also been ranked as the most effective for facing the identified agronomic and environmental challenges. This analysis, by combining prioritization and effectiveness, yielded even higher valuations than those directly assigned by stakeholders. This is conditioned by some stakeholders rating them low or not choosing them on the grounds of lack of effectiveness, incompatibility with current practices, lack of tradition, or the high implementation or management cost, so, the multi-criteria analysis really shows the true ranking. As we can see the typology of small family-run farms with elderly winemakers, with steep stony plots that make farming difficult and expensive, coupled with changes in the “terroir” due to climate change, compromises the survival of production. This study has highlighted that a change in mentality to modernise farms and adopt agro-ecological practices, as well as diversification with fodder and aromatic crops can offer the community an opportunity which, supported by marketing strategies, may provide an incentive to consumers.

Keywords

Vineyard, adoption of traditional vineyards to sustainable strategies, stakeholders' assessment, multicriteria decision.

Introduction

Agriculture in the European Union (EU) is undergoing a process change towards a more economically, socially, and environmentally sustainable production. The European Union, in considering the climate emergency we are facing, has defined in the Green Deal a framework of milestones, measures and legislative tools for the agricultural sector that aims to optimise resources use and reach a net zero balance in greenhouse gas emissions (European Commission, 2019). Adapting agricultural systems towards sustainable management practices that promote land restoration and prevent soil and land degradation represents a crucial strategy in the context of climate change, which is projected to increase the vulnerability of agricultural systems within the EU (European Union, 2013). Farmers faced with this challenge feel unprecedented pressure, a situation that is pushing growers and organisations to express their disagreement and, although they do not refuse to comply, they do seek help and greater flexibility in terms of deadlines and requirements. In such a context and because of globalisation, while EU regulations impose strict sustainability, pesticide use and animal welfare requirements on EU farmers, imported agricultural goods from third countries often don't meet equivalent criteria. Consequently, products grown outside the scope of this legislation would apparently have a competitive cost advantage over those produced on European soil. This factor must be highlighted to consumers through information and awareness-raising campaigns, without forgetting the need to search for more competitive pricing in European products through the transformation of the food sector, (European Commission, 2019)

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Within this framework, the perception of the stakeholders and their degree of knowledge and implication are essential for the transition towards sustainable European agriculture. To convince farmers of the benefits, in practice on many occasions this is posed as one of the main barriers, coupled with a lack of knowledge regarding implementation. Despite the existence of scientific consensus regarding the benefits of adopting sustainable agriculture strategies, it is true that this concept has not been successfully passed on to the productive sector and thus we find considerable uncertainty among farmers (Sidhoum *et al.*, 2023). In many cases the benefits are not readily tangible in the short term, but growers must receive the message that balanced systems provide greater benefits, even leading to reductions in costs as well as better quality, thereby solving their agronomic, economic, and environmental problems in the long term (Robinson, 2024).

Winemaking is one of the most impacted sectors by climate change in Europe, with Germany being particularly affected. The German winemaking exports industry had a turnover of 384 million Euros in 2023 (Deutsches Weininstitut (DWI), 2024), which stresses the economic and social importance of addressing its adaptation to climate change to minimise the economic, social, and environmental impact. Conclusions regarding the appropriateness of different agro-ecological strategies studied in the German agricultural and livestock sector reported in a review paper (Baaken, 2022) stated the benefits provided and highlighted the regional adequacy and the prior study of the issues and characteristics to optimise the benefits.

Over half of the surface area of Germany is currently used for agriculture. German agrifood production covers 16.7 million hectares and its annual turnover exceeds 50,000 million euros, which accounts for over one tenth of EU agricultural production. Vineyards occupy less than 1% of the agricultural land. Taking the indirect and network effects into account, around 7% of Germany's GDP comes from winemaking. Furthermore, the winemaking industry plays a key role in tourism and gastronomy, far and above its calculated economic contribution (Job and Murphy, 2006; Sottini *et al.*, 2021). Wine has become a characteristic part of Germany and German culture. (Dressler, 2018)

The Mosel winemaking region lies within the state of Rhineland-Palatinate located in south-west Germany. The area is characterised by being mostly made up of family farms run by elderly growers who cultivate in areas with steep slopes and on stony terrain. All of this gives rise to generation succession problems and high production costs (Strub and Mueller Loose, 2021) which, coupled with the lack of manual labour, increasing temperatures and frosts during the flowering period, drives the need to urgently adopt measures to ensure that this emblematic German wine is not lost. Additionally, in the wine we find a unique set of environmental factors, including climate, soil, topography, and human influence, that collectively give a wine its distinctive character and "sense of place." called "*terroir*", which all affect the final quality of the grape (Duley, 2021). We therefore see how the effects of climate change can affect both the production as well as the characteristic organoleptic quality of the wine (Dressler,

2018; Riekötter and Hassler, 2022). However, these farms generate opportunities since they are part of a characteristic landscape which has even become a tourist attraction (Dallot, 2020). Regarding agronomic and environmental aspects, in recent years temperature changes in central and southern Germany, including the Mosel region, have affected the quality of the wines produced. One solution that has been proposed involves moving the production to locations with colder temperatures and thus be able to retain their identity, referring to *terroir* characteristics, but this is no easy matter and raises numerous other associated factors, such as changing grape variety and finding hitherto unproductive zones which will have their own associated problems. In the Mosel region, erosion and soil loss are key issues due to the steep slopes; strategies to conserve agriculture through minimum tillage and the adoption of cover crops in alleys and crop lines may prove very helpful in redressing this, as has been seen in different studies carried out in the Mosel region (Kirchhoff *et al.*, 2017; Seeger *et al.*, 2019 and Riekötter and Hassler, 2022). The alleys have been managed with cover crops for years by most wine-growers in the area, but the crop lines, given their importance, are the focus of research work, such as that developed within the framework of the DIVERFARMING project (Dittrich *et al.*, 2021). This project studied the incidence on production and quality of the use of cover crops with aromatic plants in the crop line. But there are also two non-agronomic challenges to be faced: the change in mentality of the winegrower, who must adopt other farming strategies; and also, the change in consumer habits in the light of the new approaches and possible organoleptic changes in this German wine. In such a context, this study identifies low-input farming practices suitable for Mosel German vineyards by consulting relevant stakeholders. The goal is to minimize pressing agronomic, environmental, and socioeconomic issues while improving sustainability. We detail the vineyard cropping systems investigated and outline the methodology, which combines a stakeholder survey with multicriteria decision-making to determine optimal alternatives.

Material and Methods

Case study areas

The Mosel winemaking region is considered as the oldest such area in Germany (Deutsches Weininstitut, 2024). The cultivated area (Fig. 1) is located in the west of Germany, between the French-German border and the Rhine, on the banks of the Mosel River and its affluents, between Luxembourg and Koblenz, covering a surface area of 8,536 ha today (Deutsches Weininstitut web page, consulted 07/09/2024). This figure has fallen every year since 1989, when it covered a total of 12509 ha (Die Landwirtschaft 1993, 1994).

As a result of its protected geographic situation, it is one of the warmest climate zones in Germany. Frosts are avoided by the heat stored in the river, so temperature fluctuations are moderate: with slightly cold winters and warm pleasant summers with traditionally enough precipitation for the crop. According to the Köppen-Geiger classification, the climate

Figure 1. Location of Mosel region (Germany). Own elaboration.

is classified as Cfb, indicating a temperate oceanic climate. This climate is characterized by a mean annual temperature of 9.1 °C, an average annual precipitation of 722 mm, and a potential evapotranspiration rate of 687 mm per year (www.am.rlp.de; meteorological station 'Kanzem'). This mild climate, despite being at 50 degrees of latitude, gives a tremendously long growing period, from April to October, with the Riesling grape variety (*Vitis vinifera* L. 'Riesling') being the most widespread, and accounting for over 60%. A particular characteristic of these grapevines to be highlighted is that they are grown on steep slopes of between 16.7° and 68.0° (Riekötter and Hassler, 2022).

Survey to stakeholders

Perceptions of relevant stakeholders concerning the most suitable crop management alternatives for enhancing sustainability in agroecosystems were gathered using a standardized survey questionnaire developed within the H2020 DIVERFARMING project, conducted online via the Survey-Monkey platform. This questionnaire was adapted to the specific characteristics of each cropping system, informed by a literature review on diversified cropping systems and sustainable farming practices (Gómez-López *et al.*, 2019; Morugán-Coronado *et al.*, 2020).

The questionnaire contained questions organised in four blocks: 1) Stakeholder's characteristics (name, gender, type of stakeholder, affiliation, etc.); 2) Identification and assessment of the most relevant agronomic and environmental challenges specific to each crop and study area (selected from an open list), as well as an evaluation of the priority stakeholders would assign to potential actions aimed at addressing these identified problems (chosen from an open list); 3) Identification of farming practices considered appropriate by the respondent for the vineyard cropping system in the study area involved selection from a list of options, with the provision for interviewees to suggest additional practices, as in

the preceding section. For farming practices not considered suitable for a given crop/study area, stakeholders were also asked to specify the primary reason for their exclusion; and finally, 4) an assessment of the effectiveness of these farming practices in addressing the agronomic and environmental problems previously identified by the interviewee was conducted.

The stakeholders surveyed were also asked about the diversification of vineyard production through line cropping. More specifically, they were asked to select the combinations of crops that they considered as the most appropriate for intercropping in line of vineyards, considering that in the region there was already a tradition in the use of cover crops in the alleys. The introduction of selected covering of the crop line is intended to avoid weeds (Sharma *et al.*, 2021), excessive water consumption, and diseases transmitted to the grape.

Four types of stakeholders were engaged with: 1) farmers; 2) farm advisory services; 3) agricultural researchers; and 4) experts from NGOs with experience in farming. These interviewed stakeholders participated in the participatory assessment process carried out within the DIVERFARMING H2020 project's activities, in which about 250 surveys were sent out, although unfortunately not all of them were answered. The formation of the decisional group satisfied the minimum threshold for Delphi methodology, as established by Okoli and Pawlowski (2004). Participants were rigorously selected based on the expert criteria outlined by Skulmoski and Hartman (2007), which include demonstrated subject matter expertise, a propensity for active participation, and effective communication skills.

Recruitment of qualified individuals with authentic knowledge of vineyard cultivation within the defined study areas was facilitated through collaborative efforts with farmers' associations, and agribusiness entities, from whose membership databases experts were sought.

Statistical and Multicriteria assessment

As the analysed agricultural system faces different economic, agronomic and environmental problems, the evaluation of the effectiveness of agricultural practices to address these problems was performed qualitatively using linguistic labels. Stakeholders were first asked to select the most appropriate farming practices for their cropping system and region and data were statistically analyzed using STATA/SE 15. After that they also were asked to qualitatively assess the effectiveness of such practices in mitigating the agro-environmental problems in their study area. Stakeholder responses were analysed by ranking the effectiveness of farming practices through the application of multi-criteria selection techniques.

The selection of the multi-criteria decision-making approach was predicated on the requirement to convert the qualitative assessments provided by stakeholders into a quantitative format suitable for numerical analysis. This was accomplished by utilizing standardized ordinal linguistic scales with associated numerical values within the questionnaire to collect stakeholder evaluations (Munda et al., 1994).

The use of linguistic labels allows the decision maker to express his/her perception of the goodness of each alternative. It is assumed that the decision-maker is rational, in the sense of acting coherently with his/her preferences and objectives and his/her previous knowledge and expressing them through these linguistic labels. More specifically, in this study, the importance is obtained, through direct assignment, using a valuation scale with six levels that ranges from "Very low" (0) to "Very high" (5). For example, the question pattern used was "According to your criterion, the effectiveness of practice Y for addressing environmental problem X is:" (Very low, Low, Medium low, Medium high, High, Very high). Using a six-level scale is justified by the non-existence of possible neutral positions in the assessment of the severity of a problem or the effectiveness of a given farming practice, and by the need to prevent respondents with no opinion from using the middle point as a "face-saving response" instead of using the "do not know/do not answer" option (Sturgis et al., 2014).

For this study, the multicriteria model was structured around a set of agricultural practices/strategies as the alternatives for selection. Stakeholder perspectives, informed by their existing knowledge and preferences (criteria), provided the basis for evaluating the effectiveness of each alternative. The selection and evaluation of these alternatives were conducted as separate decision-making processes for each stakeholder group. To arrive at a unified prioritization of farming practices for each crop and study region (group decision), the inputs from the different stakeholder types were aggregated, with each expert group receiving equal weighting in the collective decision. The mathematical derivation of the preference ranking for farming practices employed the Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) methodology, as developed by Hwang and Yoon (1981), Zeleny (1982), and Lai et al. (1994). TOPSIS was selected due to its conceptual simplicity, intuitive logic reflecting human decision-making, and computational efficiency. This method provides a scalar value that quantifies the relative performance of each alternative with respect to both ideal

and nadir solutions, facilitating straightforward mathematical representation and visual interpretation of results. TOPSIS operates by calculating the geometric distance to an ideal solution, favouring alternatives that are closest to the Positive Ideal Solution (PIS) and furthest from the Negative Ideal Solution (NIS). These proximity indices facilitated the establishment of a priority ranking of alternatives (*i.e.*, agricultural practices) for each case study. Practices with the highest ranks were identified as the most effective in addressing the previously defined priorities. A high effectiveness rating was considered for the valuation of the results.

Results and Discussion

Main characteristics of surveyed stakeholders

A total of 34 fully-answered questionnaires were received from around 250 sent: 27 farmers, two agricultural advisors, four researchers, and one environmental NGO representative. Their average age was 49 years, while 56 years was the most frequent age. Only one stakeholder, a farmer, was female.

Assessment of agro-environmental problems and priorities for action

The stakeholders surveyed provided qualitative evaluations of the severity of various agro-environmental challenges within vineyard cropping systems. Their qualitative responses were transformed into a numerical scale ranging from 0 to 5. Key statistical measures, including the mean, median, and standard deviation, are presented in Table 1. Overall, the stakeholders perceived the severity of most agro-environmental problems to be relatively low. Table 1 shows that the loss of profitability and associated risk of farm abandonment was perceived as the most severe problem in study area, closely followed by the excessive use of phytosanitary products and biodiversity loss (Average > 2.50). In this sense, the small family farms and the elderly age of the growers is a real issue found in numerous winemaking farms throughout Europe (Lieskovský et al., 2013), associated to quality products, which drives the need for modernisation associated with technification but without losing the identity, linked to the terroir and tradition that made them characteristic, to enable them to attract young farmers or new investors (Schuetz, 2019). Farmer's associations in the region estimate that 50% of the current production level will have been abandoned in around 10 years' time. The work by Cossart et al. (2020) has also identified a similar issue in Beaujolais (France) in that the farms have decreased by 30% in regular terroirs, but by only 5% in the high added-value terroirs in 20 years. This confirms that a commitment to quality is an added value to maintain production. The same authors also highlight that higher abandonment rates occur in steep, difficult-to-maintain plots. The intensive use of phytosanitary products in most of the Mosel farms is associated to the cost of mechanically treating weeds; because of the pronounced slopes they tend to choose to use herbicides. This is put forward by the stakeholders as being a particularly highly valued

Table 1. Stakeholders' qualitative subjective assessment of the seriousness of different problems in their area (measured on a 0 to 5 scale: 0=very low/null, 5= Very high), own elaboration.

Problem assessed	Average	Median	St. Dev.
Loss of profitability/ abandonment of agriculture	2.94	3	1.50
Excessive use of phytosanitary products	2.53	2.5	1.29
Loss of biodiversity	2.44	2.5	1.44
Loss of soil organic matter	2.32	2	1.61
Excessive use of machinery	2.15	2	1.31
Excessive application of fertilisers	2.03	2	1.14
Soil degradation by erosion, pollution, etc.	1.88	2	1.52
Water pollution	1.79	2	1.12
Soil pollution	1.65	2	1.07
Land degradation	1.47	1	1.42
Excessive water use	1.38	1	1.16
Soil waterlogging	1.30	1	1.24

problem, showing their degree of implication in the search for more sustainable production. The use of a helicopter for the treatment is also associated to this, since it requires a large amount of product and causes major drift losses. To address this, new treatment strategies employing drones (Sarrí *et al.*, 2019) are proposed as an alternative in which technical assistance and appropriate permits can increase treatment precision, with the consequent environmental and economic benefits. Diversity loss is a problem that we believe to be associated with the abandonment of farms owing to retirements and increased costs and the challenges of cultivation previously highlighted by Biasi *et al.*, (2015), Rodrigo-Comino *et al.* (2018), and Cossart *et al.* (2020) in Italy, Germany and France, respectively and by the effect on insects (Böhm *et al.*, 2024; Wersebeckmann *et al.*, 2023). On the other hand, as was expected for a wet area, excessive water use was barely considered a serious problem, as was the case for land degradation and soil waterlogging (Average < 1.50). Other potential problems, such loss of soil organic matter, excessive use of machinery, excessive fertiliser application, soil degradation by erosion (Seeger, 2023), pollution, etc. and the soil pollution were also perceived as less severe problems by the surveyed stakeholders (Average between 1.51-2.49). In fact, although soil degradation and loss is a rather pronounced problem in the zone, identified in numerous studies such as those by Seeger *et al.* (2019), and we can see that it was not prioritised by the region's stakeholders, very likely because it is an area with a long-standing tradition of over 30 years in the use of cover crops in its alleys, which buffers this effect to a major degree. But in stony areas and

Table 2. Stakeholders' qualitative assessment of the priority of different objectives in Mosel German vineyards (measured on a 0 to 5 scale; 0=very low/null, 5=Very high), own elaboration.

Actions	Average	Median	St. Dev.
Conserve traditional landscapes	4.10	4	1.14
Recover traditional crops	3.88	4	1.34
Reduce soil erosion	3.28	4	1.37
Increase crop profitability	3.26	4	1.65
Increase biodiversity	3.21	3	1.41
Improve the soil structure to increase aeration and water retention and improve rooting	3.15	3	1.30
Modernise productive systems	3.06	3	1.46
Increase soil fertility	2.79	3	1.45
Reduce energy consumption	2.62	2	1.41
Increase carbon sequestration in both soil and biomass	2.09	2	1.47
Increase crop yields	2.03	2	1.31
Reduce flooding in fields	1.56	1	1.58

even in the areas where the wheels of the machinery make it impossible for cover crops to grow, the effects of erosion on the steep slopes are very pronounced in the Mosel region, as found in certain studies (Seeger *et al.*, 2019).

Following their assessment of the severity of agronomic and environmental problems, the stakeholders were then requested to provide a qualitative valuation of the priority they would assign to various potential actions aimed at addressing these issues, effectively ranking different action objectives. Their qualitative responses were transformed into a numerical scale ranging from 0 to 5, with the principal statistical data presented in Table 2. Overall, the responses aligned with the earlier identification of significant problems. As shown in Table 2, the surveyed stakeholders assigned the highest priority to the conservation of the traditional landscape and traditional crops (Mean > 3.9), closely followed by increasing crop profitability and improving soil conditions (reducing erosion, improving soil structure, and increasing soil fertility), which concurs with the vineyard sector profitability study by Bennett and Loose (2023). Stakeholders also gave relatively high priority to reducing energy consumption in Mosel wine production. These priorities clearly suggest that stakeholders recognise the need for soil conservation to be compatible with maintaining the economic viability of farms. The great concern with the conservation of traditional crops and landscapes is driven by the change that stakeholders perceive to be needed in the farms, which implies adopting measures to minimise erosion and improve the soil, which were also valued as measures to be undertaken with high priority of action (average = 3.28 and 3.15, respectively).

In this sense, the stakeholders not only value their comfort or express their aversion to change, but they are also aware that soil management and use and the traditional physical location, the “terroir”, is what stamps the organoleptic value on their wine, whilst seeking to conserve that biodiversity (Average=2.21) associated to the lands in sustainable production with cover crops and good management. The viticultural landscape plays a major role in ensuring that the direct marketing of wine in the Mosel valley works well. It is therefore also in the economic interest of the winegrower to preserve it. All this points at the recognition of the need to advance towards more sustainable production (economic, social and environmental) without losing those characteristics that differentiate wine production in the area. It is of interest that they are aware of the need for modernisation (Average=3.06), given that we believe that they see it as one of the solutions which will increase profits, marked by an average prioritisation of 3.26, together with the reduction in energy consumption (average=2.62) and increase in soil fertility (average=2.79), all of which are associated with minimising the high cultivation costs. In this context, the lack of labour/high wage level often forces mechanization. However, this is less possible for young winegrowers than for investors, whose financial background is different. As a result, wineries often become larger in terms of area so that the purchase of large machines is worthwhile. This often leads to the enlargement of individual areas and the removal of marginal and intermediate structures. This in turn has a negative impact on biodiversity and the landscape. High salaries also means that this combination of actions of modernisation, cost reduction, and increase in sustainability will make these farms more attractive to young farmers or investors who seek a value in the small farms producing quality Mosel wines and thereby provide them with continuity.

Identification of adequate farming practices for Mosel German vineyards

Participants in the survey were asked to indicate the farming practices they considered suitable for the attributes of the vineyard cropping systems within the study area. Each respondent made their selections from a list of potentially implementable farming practices, and they also had the opportunity to propose other practices not listed. For farming practices deemed unsuitable for this specific cropping system by the stakeholders, they were further asked to state the primary reason for their exclusion. Table 3 illustrates the percentage of respondents who identified each farming practice as appropriate for the cropping system, while Table 4 compiles the main reasons given for not selecting each farming practice as appropriate.

A) Limited effectiveness; B) Practice is not adequate for the characteristics of the area; C) It is not a traditional practice in the area; D) It is complex/difficult to implement without technical advice; E) It is complex/difficult to carry out even with technical advice; F) This practice is not compatible with other farming practices; G) This practice requires a high investment cost; H) The cost of carrying out this practice is high; I) The benefits of this practice do not outweigh its costs.

Own elaboration. ns=not significant. Fisher’s exact probability test analyses whether there are significant differences in the responses by stakeholder type.

First, looking at tillage practices, the results show that minimum tillage was the alternative chosen by a vast majority of the respondents as adequate, followed by use of machinery without heavy implements, which was also considered a suitable tillage practice by many stakeholders (Table 3). This is consistent with current practices in many places (Dang *et al.*, 2020) and in this area, where farmers are clearly opting to conserve soil; traditional tillage in the region is only carried out every 15 to 20 years, associated with planting, when subsoiling was carried out at 30 or 40 cm, and tillage at 10-15 cm every three or four years. With this traditional management, we could consider that most of the stakeholders already have a perception of the benefits of not carrying out these actions and of adopting minimum tillage, since the percentage of those who do not see these strategies as effective may perhaps correspond to those who continue following traditional tillage practices (Table 4). Minimum tillage in current management may be associated to turning or ploughing the topsoil in the crop lines, since weeds in the line favour the appearance of fungi and competition for water (Marzen *et al.*, 2022). In its adult stage, the grapevine pumps water from deep areas to the surface and this may attract weeds to this zone. For that reason, some studies have proposed placing aromatic species with low water consumption in the crop lines which suppress other problematic weeds but at the same time do not cause problems for the vine and the grape harvest due to their low growth height and low water consumption (Dittrich *et al.*, 2021).

Less consensus exists regarding the use of shallow tillage implements, with almost 50% of those responding considering it an adequate option. Forty percent considered no tillage with the application of herbicides in the crop line as an adequate farming practice. Lastly, only a minority of stakeholders (35%) considered no tillage with mechanical weed control, whilst tillage following contour lines was only selected by very few experts (5%). Mechanical weed control requires specific tools that most farmers do not own, and it is particularly complicated to perform on the steep slopes for the tractors with the special attachment for clearing the line with steel cables and moving it and hanging them, line by line. For that reason, research work is being undertaken in the area, aimed at demonstrating and disseminating the benefits of this practice rather than the use of herbicides. Carrying out tillage following the contour lines is impracticable except in terraced farms; these are becoming increasingly commonplace (Tarolli *et al.*, 2014), but in existing farms making terraces entails an elevated cost for implementation and the removal of the existing crop. Referring to these costs, (Strub and Mueller Loose, 2021) have identified the cost of manual or mechanised labour on the steep slopes of the vineyards as being 2.6 times higher than the cost on terraces, above all associated to the difficulty and the specialised machinery required without terracing, which even then cannot assist in all the work.

The reasons given by stakeholders for not considering the different adequate tillage practices (Table 4) were mainly due to limited effectiveness and a lack of tradition, together

Table 3. Identification of adequate farming practices (proportion of respondents identifying each practice as suitable for the vineyard cropping system in the study area)

Farming practice	Proportion of respondents	Differences by type of stakeholder (Fisher's exact test)
Tillage		
Minimum tillage	0.7941	0.525 (ns)
Use of machinery without heavy implements	0.5588	0.594 (ns)
Shallow tillage	0.5000	1.000 (ns)
No tillage with application of herbicides	0.4118	0.699 (ns)
No tillage with mechanical weed control (using brush cutter or hoe)	0.3529	0.813 (ns)
Tillage following contour lines	0.0588	1.000 (ns)
Soil cover		
Mulching (with crushed offcuts from pruning, straw, etc.)	0.8235	0.760 (ns)
Vegetation strips in alleys perpendicular to main crop	0.6471	1.000 (ns)
Cover crops	0.6471	0.905 (ns)
Rock fragments cover	0.1176	0.622 (ns)
Erosion control		
Maintaining the natural vegetation on the edges of the plots	0.5882	1.000 (ns)
Construction of erosion physical barriers with vegetation	0.3824	0.363 (ns)
Installing hedges on the edges of the plots	0.1471	0.098 (ns)
Construction of erosion barriers without vegetation	0.0882	0.277 (ns)
Fertilisation		
Use of green manure	0.7941	0.525 (ns)
Application of organic matter (manure, compost, biochar, etc)	0.7353	0.208 (ns)
Use of biostimulants and biofertilisers	0.3235	0.133 (ns)
Precision agriculture to optimise fertilisation	0.2647	0.001 (***)
Pest control		
Pheromone control	0.7941	0.780 (ns)
Integrated pest control	0.7059	0.366 (ns)
Fences and meshes to protect grapes	0.4706	0.782 (ns)

with reasons related to cost and compatibility with other tillage practices. Indeed, the steep slopes mean that these practices are not as effective as in other areas and their difficulty means that they are not traditionally adopted and are expensive to implement (Strack *et al.*, 2021). Another interesting result extracted from the answers is that hardly any stakeholders pointed out the complexity of the proposed tillage practices, nor the need for technical advice for their application, although they did point out that non-tillage with herbicide application required dosage and recommendations by agricultural technical advisors. In fact, this was probably a major barrier to adoption two decades ago, but the use of conservation tillage practices has significantly increased in the area; better machinery solutions are available, and farmers have the required experience and knowledge.

Regarding soil cover practices, for decades the tradition in the region has promoted the use of cover crops established in the alleys and in the crop lines, even alternating the green corridor to favour the machinery's path (Table 3). However, having stated that, mulching with vegetation covers (inert or alive) was the most selected practice, which more than 82% of the stakeholders considered to be as adequate, while vegetation strips and cover crops were selected in 64% of the responses, and rock fragment covers less so, only three stakeholders, owing to the predominantly stony soils. In these cases, mulching fulfils the double function of retaining the soil on the steep slopes, and helping the machinery to pass, so the cover crop is used in the alleys and lines, by crushing the pruning waste and even adding purchased shredded wood or also compost in some cases. Another important function of organic mulch is to increase the organic matter in the often poor vineyard soils. This improves the water and nutrient retention capacity of the soil.

The few stakeholders that do not consider soil cover solutions as adequate (Table 4) believe it to be quite ineffective and/or not suitable for grapevine production in the area or simply not a traditional practice. The option of covers such as walls in the alleys perpendicular to the crop could be put forward as a solution focused more on impeding erosion than in favouring the soil cover.

Erosion control is one of the main challenges facing these vineyards, as has already been mentioned, above all, in terms of soil loss. However, keeping the natural vegetation on the plot edges, and building barriers on the edges only obtained 59% and 38%, respectively, in preference (Table 3), and those that did not consider them as an option think such options have low efficiency due to the steep slopes and the difficulty in implementing them in that type of crop and plot, and the difficulty in management was the most argued as it does not fit in their farming practices (Table 4). Indeed, any erosion barrier being unable to be hooked to the attachments on the tractors on the plot edges is incompatible with their farming system.

Regarding fertilisation, the use of green manure and the application of fresh, composted, or biochar OM is widely extended, as reflected by 79% and 74%, respectively. A small proportion of stakeholders chose the use of biostimulants (32%) or precision agriculture techniques (26%), because of

Table 4. Reasons given by each respondent for not selecting each farming practice as adequate for Mosel German vineyards area (number of responses), own elaboration.

Farming practice	Reason									Total responses
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	
Tillage										
Minimum tillage	3	1	1	0	0	2	0	0	0	7
Use of machinery without heavy implements	4	1	0	0	1	2	2	3	2	15
Shallow tillage	4	5	4	0	1	0	0	2	1	17
No tillage with application of herbicides	5	5	2	2	1	2	0	2	1	20
No tillage with mechanical weed control (using brush cutter or hoe)	1	2	3	1	0	1	0	6	8	22
Tillage following contour lines	6	13	6	0	1	5	1	0	0	32
Soil cover										
Mulching (with crushed offcuts from pruning, straw, etc.)	2	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	6
Vegetation strips in alleys perpendicular to main crop	5	1	2	0	2	1	0	0	1	12
Rock fragments cover	5	9	7	3	0	0	0	3	3	30
Cover crops in alley	2	3	4	0	0	0	0	1	2	12
Erosion control										
Maintaining the natural vegetation on the edges of the plots	3	2	0	1	1	5	0	2	0	14
Construction of erosion barriers with vegetation	3	5	1	2	2	3	2	1	2	21
Installing hedges on the edges of the plots	5	8	2	2	2	7	0	2	1	29
Construction of erosion barriers without vegetation	4	6	2	3	2	6	2	4	2	31
Fertilisation										
Use of green manure	1	3	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	7
Application of organic matter (manure, compost, biochar, etc)	2	1	0	2	0	0	1	2	1	9
Use of biostimulants and biofertilisers	6	2	2	5	1	0	1	2	4	23
Precision agriculture to optimise fertilisation	5	1	0	1	4	2	2	5	5	25
Pest control										
Pheromone control	3	1	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	7
Integrated pest control	3	1	2	2	0	0	0	1	1	10
Fences and meshes to protect grapes	2	1	4	1	2	2	2	2	2	18

the high cost they would entail, and the little efficacy perceived, as reflected by those who did not choose them as alternatives (Table 4). It was also found that the farmers who did not select green manure as a good option, considering it inadequate or incompatible in their area, may have done so because their farms are very stony and so it would not grow well (Table 4). Similarly, the farmers who did not choose the contribution of organic matter as they did not consider it effective, or because it needed advice and therefore entails high costs, may be because they are growers of non-organic crops who prefer mineral fertilisation, in addition the input of nitrogen and phosphorus is much easier to control and calculate when using mineral fertilizers than when using organic fertilizers. It should be highlighted that the data in Table 4 show no statistical difference by type of stakeholder, except

for the use of precision agriculture to optimise fertilisation (Fisher's exact test = 0.001), as all researchers and public advisors considered that precision agricultural techniques are adequate for use in vineyards, in line with Bramley (2022), whilst 85% of farmers expressed the opposite opinion. Farmers, in fact, did not consider this a viable measure due to significant obstacles: high initial investment costs, lack of knowledge, insufficient expertise, and inadequate technological infrastructure (Latherow *et al.*, 2024). Their limited resources for extensive farm digitalization, coupled with the advanced age of many growers, further complicate such adoption. Therefore, facilitating knowledge transfer through training centers or successful pilot farmer initiatives, such as the living labs or lighthouses proposed in Horizon Europe research calls, could overcome these barriers.

Regarding pest control, the use of pheromones (79%) and integrated control (70%) were the most valued practices, as opposed to the use of barriers to protect the grape, such as nets or electric barriers (47%), which involve an elevated cost. However, those stakeholders who did not select those options considered that they are ineffective measures, are incompatible with the current crop, are not a tradition in the area, involve a cost and consider that they lack the knowledge to introduce them.

Rating of the effectiveness of farming practices

Lastly, the survey asked stakeholders to qualitatively assess the effectiveness of the farming practices to address the agro-environmental problems identified in their area. It must be noted that this question was only answered for any specific farming practice by those stakeholders who considered such a practice as suitable for implementation in the Mosel vineyard region. Table 5 shows the rating of preferences for farming practices resulting from the TOPSIS multicriteria analysis (relative closeness indexes). A higher closeness index means that the corresponding farming practice was considered as more effective by the surveyed stakeholders.

Respondents were asked to assess the effectiveness to address the agro-environmental problems in their area of each of the farming practice that each of them had previously selected as adequate for the corresponding study crop.

The ranking for ordering farming practices from the multicriteria assessment (Table 5) might seem to be the same as that presented in Table 3, yet there are certain differences, as the farming practices most selected as adequate were not necessarily those evaluated as being more effective by the stakeholders. It must also be noted that the indexes resulting from the multicriteria assessment were very high for many of the farming practices, so the results enable the most effective alternatives to be selected, which do not always coincide in order or magnitude with those in Table 3. Considering tillage practices, minimum tillage was rated as being the most effective alternative for addressing the major agro-environmental problems, followed at a significant distance by shallow tillage and the use of machinery without heavy implements. This is consistent with current practices in the study area, where minimum tillage is still more widespread than no tillage, which, in certain conditions, is subject to some factors which restrict its adoption (Soane *et al.*, 2012). Regarding these practices, the review by Baaken (2022) highlighted that the bibliographical studies consulted and focused on Germany see these practices as having a positive impact on the soil, water, and biodiversity, coinciding with the environmental problems noted by the stakeholders.

Regarding soil cover alternatives, the results were like those in Table 3, with the use of mulching as the most effective alternative for stakeholders. It should be noted that in this case there was less difference in the preference for using mulching and the following alternatives of vegetation strips in the alleys and nearby cover crops, with rock fragments offering scant effectiveness. In this case, the compilation of environmental benefits carried out by Baaken (2022) stressed that these practices offer a clear benefit on climate change and

Table 5. Stakeholders' qualitative assessment of the effectiveness of each of the farming practices to face the agro-environmental problems in the Mosel German vineyard zone (relative closeness indexes from the TOPSIS multicriteria assessment), own elaboration.

Farming practice	TOPSIS ranking
Tillage	
Minimum tillage	0.80
Shallow tillage	0.47
Use of machinery without heavy implements	0.46
No tillage with application of herbicides	0.41
No tillage with mechanical weed control	0.41
Tillage following contour lines	0.05
Soil cover	
Mulching (with crushed offcuts from pruning, straw, etc.)	0.79
Vegetation strips in alleys perpendicular to main crop	0.70
Cover crops	0.68
Rock fragments cover	0.21
Erosion control	
Maintaining the natural vegetation on the edges of the plots	0.75
Construction of erosion barriers with vegetation	0.40
Installing hedges on the edges of the plots	0.42
Construction of erosion barriers without vegetation	0.00
Fertilisation	
Use of green manure	0.74
Application of organic matter (manure, compost, biochar, etc)	0.60
Use of biostimulants and biofertilisers	0.44
Precision agriculture to optimise fertilisation	0.49
Pest control	
Integrated pest control	0.59
Pheromone control	0.46
Fences and meshes to protect grapes	0.47

biodiversity, with some of them being marked as environmental problems in the region which has also been studied by Castillo *et al.*, (2025) in the wine-growing areas of Mexico. In the multicriteria selection ranking obtained for erosion control, the high effectiveness of maintaining the natural vegetation on the edges of the plots should be highlighted; its values exceeded those obtained in Table 3. As we have stated this would point more to a practice with a different value for its suitability to the area (Table 3) than to its effectiveness in

solving the agro-environmental problems identified (Table 5). In this case the multicriteria valuation further highlighted its effectiveness, but as already mentioned the particularity of the mechanisation of the work with attached machinery carried out by tractors at the plot edges, makes it impracticable. The following alternatives referring to construction of erosion barriers with vegetation and installing hedges on the edges of the plots showed a low average effectiveness according to the data obtained. This coincides with Baaken (2022) about the environmental benefits of these practices, but it was also concluded that they must be studied in each area to tailor them to its particularities. Likewise, null effectivity was obtained for the construction of erosion barriers without vegetation, coinciding with the opinions expressed in Table 3, based on the limitation by the characteristics of the terrain and current practices.

Regarding fertilisation, the results point to the need for green manure use, where adding exogenous biofertiliser was perceived as the most effective fertilisation alternative. Lastly, despite the relevance given to soil conservation as a priority objective in the study area, the alternative for the application of organic matter was considered to present medium effectiveness, with values obtained which were close to those in Table 3. The use of biostimulants and precision agriculture received similar low effectiveness ratings and were considered the least effective fertilisation alternatives, with values of 0.44 and 0.49, respectively. These results coincide with those of Baaken (2022) and the positive effects of these practices for the climate, soil, and water linked to the agro-environmental problems in the Mosel region. In these latter cases, the values for effectiveness were higher than those shown in Table 3, to the point of being 50% higher in precision agriculture. It should be highlighted that, as mentioned before, these are two efficient and necessary practices, but which require a greater initial investment and for growers to be more specialised (Bramley, 2022). Therein lies the discrepancy between technicians and farmers seen in Table 3, which the TOPSIS methodology balances out when the group decision considers equal weighting for each type of stakeholder.

Lastly, integrated pest control techniques were considered as a medium effective alternative for this cropping system. The stakeholders saw this practice as being appropriate to apply in this area and it was therefore well valued. Likewise, the use of pheromones, although it achieved a better valuation in the effectiveness ranking, with a medium value, failed to reach the values of nearly 0.8 presented in Table 3. This fact

could be justified because, despite the health problems associated with the proliferation of fungi, the stakeholders did not consider it to be a problem to be solved using management strategies; in that sense the control in ecological agriculture is carried out with copper, sulfur, rock powder and plant extracts for a physical barrier against fungal spores and strengthening the leaves and in the conventional system with preventive treatments to impede propagation.

Overall, all the alternatives for addressing the major agro-environmental problems in the study area imply a reduction in the frequency of tillage, the use of mulching, green manure, integrated pest control, and maintaining the natural vegetation on the edges of the plots and are in line with the recommendations to promote ecosystems services in agricultural systems (Duru *et al.*, 2015).

Identification of the most appropriate diversification crops

Each stakeholder chose a maximum of two possible crop combinations from an open list or indicated alternative combinations. Table 6 also shows the number of stakeholders that selected each crop type. In general, the results showed a preference for “Mix of fodder species (Poaceae, Leguminosae, Cruciferae)” (28 stakeholders), as opposed to aromatic crops (9 respondents) and to “Native grass” (8 respondents).

Each stakeholder chose a maximum of two possible diversification crops. The first three rows correspond to respondents that only gave one answer, while the other two rows correspond to those that gave two answers. Fisher’s exact test = 0.573 (ns)

To a certain extent, these are diversification strategies which, although they have been chosen by the stakeholders, present some limitations in their practical application. Regarding intercropping associated with forage crops, grazing would be limited to ruminants that do not have grapes as part of their diet, since the introduction of such animals could negatively affect production. Similarly, the implantation of aromatic plants (Dittrich *et al.*, 2021) is proposed as a diversification, which contributes extra income for the farm but must be supported by accompanying help in selling or marketing the product (Bennett and Loose, 2023). The market for essential oils and aromatic derivatives is booming and could represent an extra income for farms. This type of initiative would be

Table 6. Type of diversification crops selected per stakeholder type, own elaboration.

Type of diversification crops selected	Farmers	Agricultural advisors	Researchers	Environmental NGOs	TOTAL
Mix of fodder species (Poaceae, Leguminosae, Cruciferae)	11	2	3	1	17
Aromatic crops	5	0	0	0	5
Native grass	0	0	1	0	1
Mix of fodder species or Aromatic crops	4	0	0	0	4
Mix of fodder species or Native grass	7	0	0	0	7
TOTAL	27	2	4	1	34

aimed at a market that is more concerned with sustainability and circular economy, or even tourism (Dallot, 2020; Job and Murphy, 2006) and in which these aromatic essences would obtain a higher price supported by marketing strategies (Schuetz, 2019). Such strategies could give them a value associated to a brand image and even linked to aspects of social responsibility for developing local economies, given that both the wine as well as its sub-products are usually marketed directly in the winery (Sottini *et al.*, 2021). The economic valuation of maintaining these line crops must also be taken into account, although in many cases, it would be compensated by the absence of weed management, given the competition these covers establish and that they displace the weeds in the alleys.

Conclusions

The results highlight local stakeholders' views on how to steer grapevine growing systems toward more sustainable production in the study area. Stakeholders agreed on the problems and challenges faced, as well as agricultural practices they deemed most appropriate. Nonetheless, a clear divide exists between those who recognise the need for modern practices focused on environmental, economic, and social sustainability, and those farmers reluctant to move away from traditional cultivation methods. Stakeholders emphasized the importance of reconciling farming traditions and quality identity with economic viability and preventing farm abandonment. Environmental issues like soil erosion and preserving traditional crops were also prominent concerns. Focusing on farm profitability was clearly evident from their preferences for sustainable practices. For example, the preferred choice of minimum tillage combines soil conservation with cost and time savings, especially because tillage on steep slopes is complicated (Strub and Mueller Loose, 2021). The tradition of using cover crops in alleys influenced their responses, although some farmers still preferred conventional and more costly tillage practices. Mulching was favoured over more expensive permanent soil conservation structures such as hedges, terraces, and stone walls, as they were considered impractical due to high costs, steep slopes, and incompatibility with machinery use on plot edges. Despite soil erosion being a major concern, stakeholders found the proposed solutions ineffective due to implementation difficulties on steep slopes and incompatibility with their usual farming practices (Strub and Mueller Loose, 2021). Concerning fertilisation, there was consensus on the need to shift to organic sources, like green manure, manure, or compost. However, significant discrepancy emerged between farmers and technicians regarding the use of precision agriculture. Farmers cited cost and lack of knowledge as barriers, while technicians saw no such obstacles, pointing to a gap in knowledge transfer and to the perceived benefits of those technologies. Crop health was not viewed as significant, with preventive measures for fungal problems being prioritised over agro-ecological solutions. Regarding intercropping, stakeholders favoured forage species over aromatic plants for their ability to reduce weeds, minimise herbicide use, and reduce competition with grapevines for resources. However, introducing ruminants for grazing may endanger grape production, while aromatic

crops could generate profit if their extracts were properly marketed. In conclusion, the economic sustainability of these vineyards and the identity of their wines depend on a shift in mindset among growers, supported by technicians and technological advancements. Changes in consumer attitudes could further encourage farmers to adopt environmentally sustainable and diversified farming practices that contribute to facing the agro-climatic and economic threats to wine production in the area. In addition, direct marketing in the Mosel area through ecotourism strategies could positively influence this transition, as consumers could link environmentally friendly agricultural practices with wine producers.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest. The funders had no role in the design of the study; in the collection, analyses, or interpretation of data; in the writing of the manuscript, or in the decision to publish the results.

References

- Baaken, M. C., 2022:** Sustainability of agricultural practices in Germany: a literature review along multiple environmental domains. *Regional Environmental Change*, 22(39), 1–19 DOI: 10.1007/s10113-022-01892-5.
- Bennett, A. W., Loose, S. M., 2023:** Benchmarking Economic Sustainability: What Factors Explain Heterogeneity between Wine Businesses? *Sustainability*, 15(24), 16686. DOI: 10.3390/su152416686.
- Biasi, R. and Brunori, E., 2015:** The on-farm conservation of grapevine (*Vitis vinifera* L.) landraces assures the habitat diversity in the viticultural agro-ecosystem. *VITIS - Journal of Grapevine Research*. 54, 265–269. DOI: 10.5073/vitis.2015.54.special-issue.265-269.
- Böhm, L., Krahner, A., Porten, M., Maixner, M., Schäffer, J., Schmitt, T., 2024:** Crossing Old Concepts: The Ecological Advantages of New Vineyard Types. *Diversity (Basel)*, 16. DOI: 10.3390/d16010044.
- Bramley, R. G. V., 2022:** Precision Viticulture: Managing vineyard variability for improved quality outcomes. In: Reynolds A.G. (Eds). *Managing Wine Quality*. Elsevier, Amsterdam. 541–586. DOI: 10.1016/B978-0-08-102067-8.00002-6.
- Cossart, E., Pic, J., Le Guen, Y., Fressard, M., 2020:** Spatial Patterns of Vineyard Abandonment and Related Land Use Transitions in Beaujolais (France): A Multiscale Approach. *Sustainability*, 12(11), 1–21. DOI: 10.3390/su12114695.
- Dallot, S., 2020:** Le paysage culturel, nouveau paradigme de réémergence du vignoble allemand en vallées du Haut-Rhin Moyen et de la Moselle. *Pour N° 237-238*, 241–253. DOI: 10.3917/pour.237.0241.

- Dang, Y. P., Page, K. L., Dalal, R. C., Menzies, N. W., 2020:** No-till Farming Systems for Sustainable Agriculture: An overview. In: Dang, Y.P., Dalal, R.C., Menzies, N.W., (Eds). No-till Farming Systems for Sustainable Agriculture: Challenges and Opportunities. Springer International Publishing. Cham (Suiza). DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-46409-7.
- Deutsches Weininstitut (DWI). 2024:** Deutscher Wein Statistik. https://www.deutscheweine.de/fileadmin/DWI/News_Medien/Publikationen/Deutscher_Wein_Statistik/Statistik_2024-2025-KW8.pdf. (Consulted 07/09/2025).
- Die Landwirtschaft 1993, 1994:** Statistisches Landesamt Rheinland-Pfalz. Bad Ems, Germany.
- Dittrich, F., Iserloh, T., Treseler, C. H., Hüppi, R., Ogan, S., Seeger, M., Thiele-Bruhn, S., 2021:** Crop diversification in viticulture with aromatic plants: Effects of intercropping on grapevine productivity in a steep-slope vineyard in the Mosel area, Germany. *Agriculture (Switzerland)* 11, 1–15. DOI: 10.3390/agriculture11020095.
- Dressler, M., 2018:** The German Wine Market: A Comprehensive Strategic and Economic Analysis. *Beverages*, 4(4)92. DOI: 10.3390/beverages4040092.
- Duley, G., 2021:** The Impact of Temperature on 'Pinot Noir' Berry and Wine Quality in a Steeply Sloping Cool Climate Vineyard in South Australia. *Vitis - Journal of Grapevine Research*, 60(4), 169–178. DOI: 10.5073/vitis.2021.60.169-178.
- Duru, M., Therond, O., Martin, G., Martin-Clouaire, R., Magne, M. A., Justes, E., Journet, E. P., Aubertot, J. N., Savary, S., Bergez, J. E., Sarthou, J. P., 2015:** How to implement biodiversity-based agriculture to enhance ecosystem services: a review. *Agronomy Sustainable Development*, 35, 1259–1281. DOI: 10.1007/s13593-015-0306-1.
- European Commission, 2019:** A European Green Deal | European Commission.
- European Union, 2013:** Regulation (EU) No 1307/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 Establishing Rules for Direct Payments to Farmers Under Support Schemes Within the Framework of the Common Agricultural Policy and Repealing Council Regulation.
- Gómez-López, M. D., Martínez-Granados, D., Calatrava, J., 2019:** Deliverable 2.1. Outcomes of the multicriteria model for decision making. EU Horizon 2020 DIVERFARMING Project, Grant Agreement N° 728003.
- Hwang, C. L., Yoon, K., 1981:** Multiple Attribute Decision Making. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-642-48318-9.
- Job, H., Murphy, A., 2006:** Germany's Mosel Valley: Can Tourism Help Preserve Its Cultural Heritage? *Tourism Review International*, 9, 333–347. DOI: 10.3727/154427206776330526.
- Kirchhoff, M., Rodrigo-Comino, J., Seeger, M., Ries, J. B., 2017:** Soil erosion in sloping vineyards under conventional and organic land use managements (Saar-Mosel Valley, Germany). *Cuadernos de Investigación Geográfica* 43, 119–140. DOI: 10.18172/cig.3161.
- Lai, Y. J., Liu, T. Y., Hwang, C. L., 1994:** TOPSIS for MODM. *European Journal Operational Research*, 76, 486–500. DOI: 10.1016/0377-2217(94)90282-8.
- Latherow, T., Arnoult, M., Engel, T., Graf, R., Hrynevych, O., Karampoiki, M., Mahmood, S., Murdoch, A., Para-foros, D., Ranieri, E., Todman, L., Tranter, R., Hammond, J. 2024:** Optimising Precision Agriculture Choices for Arable Farmers in Germany and the UK: the LINKDAPA Approach. *EuroChoices*, 23(3), 29–35. DOI: 10.1111/1746-692X.12426.
- Lieskovský, J., Kanka, R., Bezák, P., Štefunková, D., Petrovič, F., Dobrovodská, M., 2013:** Driving forces behind vineyard abandonment in Slovakia following the move to a market-oriented economy. *Land use policy* 32, 356–365. DOI: 10.1016/j.landusepol.2012.11.010.
- Marzen, M., Porten, M., Ries, J. B., 2022:** Quantification of Dust Emissions during Tillage Operations in Steep Slope Vineyards in the Moselle Area. *Agriculture (Switzerland)*, 12. DOI: 10.3390/agriculture12010100.
- Morugán-Coronado, A., Linares, C., Gómez-López, M. D., Faz, Á., Zornoza, R., 2020:** The impact of intercropping, tillage and fertilizer type on soil and crop yield in fruit orchards under Mediterranean conditions: A meta-analysis of field studies. *Agricultural Systems*, 178, 102736. DOI: 10.1016/j.agry.2019.102736.
- Munda, G., Nijkamp, P., Rietveld, P., 1994:** Qualitative multicriteria evaluation for environmental management. *Ecological Economics*, 10, 97–112. DOI: 10.1016/0921-8009(94)90002-7.
- Okoli, C., Pawlowski, S. D., 2004:** The Delphi method as a research tool: an example, design considerations and applications. *Information & Management*, 42, 15–29. DOI: 10.1016/j.im.2003.11.002.
- Riekötter, N., Hassler, M., 2022:** Agroforestry Systems in Wine Production-Mitigating Climate Change in the Mosel Region. *Forests*, 13(11). DOI: 10.3390/f13111755.
- Robinson, G. M., 2024.** Global sustainable agriculture and land management systems. *Geography and Sustainability*, 5 (4), 637–646. DOI: 10.1016/j.geosus.2024.09.001.
- Rodrigo-Comino, J., Neumann, M., Remke, A., Ries, J. B., 2018:** Assessing environmental changes in abandoned German vineyards. Understanding key issues for restoration management plans. *Hungarian Geographical Bulletin* 67, 319–332. DOI: 10.15201/hungeobull.67.4.2.
- Sarri, D., Martelloni, L., Rimediotti, M., Lisci, R., Lombardo, S., Vieri, M., 2019:** Testing a multi-rotor unmanned aerial vehicle for spray application in high slope terraced vineyard. *Journal of Agricultural Engineering* 50, 38–47. DOI: 10.4081/jae.2019.853.
- Schuetz, T., 2019:** The Development of Winegrowing, Wine-making and Distribution of Wine in the Lower Moselle (Eighteenth–Twentieth Centuries). In: Conca Mesiiina, S., Le Bras, A. S., Tedeschi, P., Vaquero Piñeiro, M. A history of wine in Europe, 19th and 20th Centuries, Vol II., 77–101. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-27772-7_4.
- Seeger, M., 2023:** Agricultural Soil Degradation in Germany. *Handbook of Environmental Chemistry*, 121, 87–103. DOI: 10.1007/698_2022_948/COVER.
- Seeger, M., Rodrigo-Comino, J., Iserloh, T., Brings, C., Ries, J. B., 2019:** Dynamics of runoff and soil erosion on abandoned

steep vineyards in the Mosel Area, Germany. *Water (Switzerland)* 11. DOI: 10.3390/w11122596.

Sharma, G., Shrestha, S., Kunwar, S., Tseng, T. M., 2021: Crop diversification for improved weed management: A review. *Agriculture (Switzerland)*, 11(5). DOI: 10.3390/agriculture11050461.

Sidhoum, A. A., Mennig, P., Sauer, J., 2023: Do agri-environment measures help improve environmental and economic efficiency? Evidence from Bavarian dairy farmers, *European Review of Agricultural Economics*, 50 (3), 918–953. DOI: 10.1093/erae/jbad007.

Skulmoski, G. J., Hartman, F. T., Krahn, J. 2007: The Delphi method for graduate research. *Journal of Information Technology Education: Research*, 6 (1), 1–21. DOI: 10.28945/199.

Soane, B. D., Ball, B. C., Arvidsson, J., Basch, G., Moreno, F., Roger-Estrade, J., 2012: No-till in northern, western and south-western Europe: A review of problems and opportunities for crop production and the environment. *Soil Tillage Research*, 118, 66–87. DOI: 10.1016/j.still.2011.10.015.

Sottini, V. A., Barbierato, E., Bernetti, I., Capecchi, I., 2021: Impact of climate change on wine tourism: An approach through social media data. *Sustainability (Switzerland)* 13(13), 7489. DOI: 10.3390/su13137489.

Strack, T., Schmidt, D., Stoll, M., 2021: Impact of steep slope management system and row orientation on canopy microclimate. Comparing terraces to downslope vineyards. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*, 307(15), 108515. DOI: 10.1016/j.agrformet.2021.108515.

Strub, L., Mueller Loose, S., 2021: The cost disadvantage of steep slope viticulture and strategies for its preservation. *OENO One* 55, 49–68. DOI: 10.20870/oeno-one.2021.55.1.4494.

Sturgis, P., Roberts, C., Smith, P., 2014: Middle Alternatives Revisited. *Sociological Methods and Research*, 43, 15–38. DOI: 10.1177/0049124112452527.

Tarolli, P., Preti, F., Romano, N., 2014: Terraced landscapes: From an old best practice to a potential hazard for soil degradation due to land abandonment. *Anthropocene*, 6, 10–25. DOI: 10.1016/j.ancene.2014.03.002.

Wersebeckmann, V., Warzecha, D., Entling, M..H., Leyer, I., 2023: Contrasting effects of vineyard type, soil and landscape factors on ground- versus above-ground-nesting bees. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 60, 601–613. DOI: 10.1111/1365-2664.14358.

Zeleny, M., 1982: *Multiple Criteria Decision-Making*, 1st ed. McGraw-Hill, New York.